

Supporting Information

for

Low-temperature direct oxidation of propane to propylene oxide using supported subnanometer Cu clusters

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Figure. S1. Rate of formation (a) and carbon based selectivity (b) for reaction products propylene, propylene oxide and the byproducts CO , and CO_2 during oxidative dehydrogenation of propane over Cu_4 clusters on UNCD support (2% propane and 2% oxygen in He under 1.1 atm).

Figure S2. GIXANES spectra of supported Cu clusters of different sizes during oxidative dehydrogenation of propane collected at the Cu K-edge (2% propane and 2% oxygen in He under 1.1 atm). XANES spectra for (a) Cu_4 on alumina, (b) Cu_4 on UNCD, (c) Cu_{12} on alumina, and (d) Cu_{20} on alumina.

Figure S3. Cu K-edge XANES spectra of bulk Cu standards used for linear combination fit of the Cu K-edge spectra of Cu_n clusters

Figure S4. XANES analysis for Cu₄ clusters on UNCD supports at Cu K-edge (2%propane and 2% oxygen in He under 1.1 atm). (a) XANES spectra were collected at the Cu K-edge as shown in Fig. S3b and LCF fitting was performed with the Cu standards shown in Fig. S3 to obtain the composition.(b) Oxidation state of Cu in the Cu₄ clusters.

Figure S5. GISAXS spectra of supported Cu clusters during oxidative dehydrogenation of propane collected at 9.1 keV (2%propane and 2% oxygen in He under 1.1 atm). GISAXS spectra for (a) Cu₄ on alumina, (b) Cu₄ on UNCD, (c) Cu₁₂ on alumina, (d) Cu₂₀ on alumina.

Figure S6. Computed total energy profile (not to scale) for the gas phase conversion of propane to propene by a Cu_4O_4 catalyst in the gas phase at the $\omega\text{b97x-d/TZVPD}$ level of theory. All energies are given in eV with reference to infinitely separated Cu_4O_4 and propane. The C^\ddagger and E^\ddagger are transition state structures. Note that the lowest energy state of Cu_4O_4 (A) corresponds to planar quintet state, while lowest energy structure of $\text{Cu}_4\text{O}_4\text{H}_2$ (G) corresponds to triplet electronic state.

Figure S7. O_2 dissociation on hydroxylated amorphous alumina-supported Cu_4O_2 , chosen as a representative model for the oxidized clusters, to recover the Cu_4O_4 cluster stoichiometry.

Figure S8. The phase diagram of the hydroxylated copper oxide cluster. The x-axis is the temperature in Celsius and y-axis is the partial pressure of oxygen in the log scale. The partial pressure of H₂O is assumed to be always 1 percent of the P(O₂) (subfigure (a)) and 10 percent of P(O₂) (subfigure (a)) respectively.

Figure S9. Energies of intermediates and transition states for the side reaction of acrolein formation from propylene.